

20899, telephone number (301) 975-2361.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: The Assistant Secretary for Administration, with the concurrence of the General Counsel, formally determined on April 5, 2012, that the meeting of the Judges Panel may be closed in accordance with 5 U.S.C. 552b(c)(4) because the meeting is likely to disclose trade secrets and commercial or financial information obtained from a person which is privileged or confidential and 5 U.S.C. 552b(c)(9)(B) because for a government agency the meetings are likely to disclose information that could significantly frustrate implementation of a proposed agency action. The meeting, which involves examination of Award applicant data from U.S. companies and other organizations and a discussion of these data as compared to the Award criteria in order to recommend the 2012 Baldrige Award recipients, may be closed to the public.

Dated: October 2, 2012.

Phillip Singerman,

Associate Director for Innovation & Industry Services.

[FR Doc. 2012-24915 Filed 10-9-12; 8:45 am]

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DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE

National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

[Docket Number 120928506-2506-01]

RIN 0648-XC276

Science Advisory Board Satellite Task Force; Availability of Draft Report and Request for Comments

AGENCY: Office of Oceanic and Atmospheric Research (OAR), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), Department of Commerce (DOC).

ACTION: Notice of availability and request for public comment.

SUMMARY: NOAA Office of Oceanic and Atmospheric Research (OAR) publishes this notice on behalf of the NOAA Science Advisory Board (SAB) to announce the availability of the draft report of the SAB Satellite Task Force (here called the SATTF) for public comment. The draft report of the SATTF has been prepared at NOAA's request made in September 2011. The NOAA National Environmental Satellite, Data, and Information Service (NESDIS) asked the SAB to review the existing and planned satellite programs and consider proposed alternatives to them. This report provides findings and

recommendations from the SATTF on this topic.

DATES: Comments on this draft report must be received by 5 p.m. on November 9, 2012.

ADDRESSES: The Draft Report of the SATTF will be available on the NOAA Science Advisory Board Web site at www.sab.noaa.gov/Reports/satf.html. The public is encouraged to submit comments electronically to noaa.sab.comments2@noaa.gov. For individuals who do not have access to the Internet, comments may be submitted in writing to: NOAA Science Advisory Board (SAB) c/o Dr. Cynthia Decker, 1315 East-West Highway-R/SAB, Silver Spring, Maryland 20910. **FOR FURTHER INFORMATION CONTACT:** Dr. Cynthia Decker, Executive Director, Science Advisory Board, NOAA, 1315 East-West Highway-R/SAB, Silver Spring, Maryland 20910. (Phone: 301-734-1156, Fax: 301-734-1459) during normal business hours of 9 a.m. to 5 p.m. Eastern Time, Monday through Friday, or visit the NOAA SAB Web site at <http://www.sab.noaa.gov>.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: For more information on the charge of the SATTF, please visit the SAB Web site: http://www.sab.noaa.gov/Working_Groups/current/SATTF%20TOR%20NOAA%20FINAL.pdf.

The SAB is chartered under the Federal Advisory Committee Act and is the only Federal Advisory Committee with the responsibility to advise the Under Secretary of NOAA on long- and short-term strategies for research, education, and application of science to resource management and environmental assessment and prediction.

NOAA welcomes all comments on the content of the draft report. We also request comments on any inconsistencies perceived within the report, and possible omissions of important topics or issues. This draft report is being issued for comment only and is not intended for interim use. For any shortcoming noted within the report, please propose specific remedies. Suggested changes will be incorporated where appropriate, and a final report will be posted on the SAB Web site prior to the November 2012 SAB meeting.

Please follow these instructions for preparing and submitting comments. Using the format guidance described below will facilitate the processing of comments and assure that all comments are appropriately considered. Overview comments should be provided first and should be numbered. Comments that are specific to particular pages, paragraphs

or lines of the section should follow any overview comments and should identify the page and line numbers to which they apply. Please number each page of your comments.

Dated: October 2, 2012.

Andy Baldus,

Acting Chief Financial Officer/Chief Administrative Officer, Office of Oceanic and Atmospheric Research, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration.

[FR Doc. 2012-24864 Filed 10-9-12; 8:45 am]

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DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE

National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

RIN 0648-XC281

Endangered and Threatened Species; Initiation of 5-Year Review for Kemp's Ridley, Olive Ridley, Leatherback, and Hawksbill Sea Turtles

AGENCY: National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), Commerce.

ACTION: Notice of initiation of 5-year review; request for information.

SUMMARY: NMFS announces 5-year reviews of Kemp's ridley (*Lepidochelys kempii*), olive ridley (*Lepidochelys olivacea*), leatherback (*Dermochelys coriacea*), and hawksbill (*Eretmochelys imbricata*) sea turtles under the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (ESA). A 5-year review is based on the best scientific and commercial data available at the time of the review; therefore, we are requesting submission of any such information on these sea turtles that has become available since that has become available since their last status review in 2007.

DATES: To allow us adequate time to conduct this review, we must receive your information no later than December 10, 2012. However, we will continue to accept new information about any listed species at any time.

ADDRESSES: You may submit comments on this document, identified by NOAA-NMFS-2012-0196, by any of the following methods:

- **Electronic Submissions:** Submit all electronic public comments via the Federal e-Rulemaking Portal www.regulations.gov. To submit comments via the e-Rulemaking Portal, first click the "submit a comment" icon, then enter NOAA-NMFS-2012-0196 in the keyword search. Locate the document you wish to comment on

from the resulting list and click on the "Submit a Comment" icon on the right of that line.

- *Mail or hand-delivery:* Angela Somma, National Marine Fisheries Service, Office of Protected Resources, Endangered Species Division, 1325 East West Highway, Silver Spring, MD 20910.

Instructions: Comments must be submitted by one of the above methods to ensure that the comments are received, documented, and considered by NMFS. Comments sent by any other method, to any other address or individual, or received after the end of the comment period, may not be considered. All comments received are a part of the public record and will generally be posted for public viewing on www.regulations.gov without change. All personal identifying information (e.g., name, address, etc.) submitted voluntarily by the sender will be publicly accessible. Do not submit confidential business information, or otherwise sensitive or protected information. NMFS will accept anonymous comments (enter "N/A" in the required fields if you wish to remain anonymous). Attachments to electronic comments will be accepted in Microsoft Word or Excel, WordPerfect, or Adobe PDF file formats only.

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION CONTACT: Larissa Plants, Office of Protected Resources, 301-427-8471.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: Section 4(c)(2)(A) of the ESA requires that we conduct a review of listed species at least once every five years. The regulations in 50 CFR 424.21 require that we publish a notice in the **Federal Register** announcing those species currently under active review. This notice announces our active review of the Kemp's ridley, olive ridley, leatherback, and hawksbill sea turtles.

Public Solicitation of New Information

To ensure that the 5-year review is complete and based on the best available scientific and commercial information, we are soliciting new information from the public, governmental agencies, Tribes, the scientific community, industry, environmental entities, and any other interested parties concerning the status of Kemp's ridley, olive ridley, leatherback, and hawksbill sea turtles. The 5-year review considers the best scientific and commercial data and all new information that has become available since the listing determination or most recent status review. Categories of requested information include: (1) Species biology including, but not

limited to, population trends, distribution, abundance, demographics, and genetics; (2) habitat conditions including, but not limited to, amount, distribution, and suitability; (3) conservation measures that have been implemented that benefit the species; (4) status and trends of threats; and (5) other new information, data, or corrections including, but not limited to, taxonomic or nomenclatural changes, identification of erroneous information contained in the List of Endangered and Threatened Species, and improved analytical methods.

Any new information will be considered during the 5-year review and will also be useful in evaluating the ongoing recovery program for these sea turtles. For example, information on conservation measures will assist in tracking implementation of recovery actions.

Authority: 16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*

Dated: October 3, 2012.

Heather Coll,

Acting Chief, Endangered Species Division, Office of Protected Resources, National Marine Fisheries Service.

[FR Doc. 2012-24935 Filed 10-9-12; 8:45 am]

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DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE

National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

National Climate Assessment and Development Advisory Committee; Meeting

AGENCY: Office of Oceanic and Atmospheric Research (OAR), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), Department of Commerce (DOC).

ACTION: Notice of open meeting.

SUMMARY: This notice sets forth the schedule of a forthcoming meeting of the DoC NOAA National Climate Assessment and Development Advisory Committee (NCADAC).

DATES: *Time and Date:* The meeting will be held Wednesday, October 24, 2012 from 3-5 p.m. Eastern time.

PLACE: This meeting will be a conference call. Public access will be available at the office of the U.S. Global Change Research Program, Conference Room A, Suite 250, 1717 Pennsylvania Avenue NW., Washington, DC 20006. The public will not be able to dial into the call. Please check the National Climate Assessment Web site for additional information at <http://www.globalchange.gov/what-we-do/assessment>.

Status

The meeting will be open to public participation with a 10-minute public comment period from 4:45-4:55 p.m. The NCADAC expects that public statements presented at its meetings will not be repetitive of previously submitted verbal or written statements. In general, each individual or group making a verbal presentation will be limited to a total time of two minutes. Written comments should be received in the NCADAC DFO's office by Friday, October 19, 2012, to provide sufficient time for NCADAC review. Written comments received by the NCADAC DFO after Friday, October 19, 2012, will be distributed to the NCADAC, but may not be reviewed prior to the meeting date.

Special Accommodations

These meetings are physically accessible to people with disabilities. Requests for special accommodations may be directed no later than 12 p.m. on Friday, October 19, 2012, to Dr. Cynthia Decker, Designated Federal Official, National Climate Assessment and Development Advisory Committee, NOAA, Rm. 11230, 1315 East-West Highway, Silver Spring, Maryland 20910, (Phone: 301-734-1156, Fax: 301-713-1459, Email: Cynthia.Decker@noaa.gov.)

Matters to be Considered

Please refer to the Web page <http://www.nesdis.noaa.gov/NCADAC/index.html> for the most up-to-date meeting agenda, when available.

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION: The National Climate Assessment and Development Advisory Committee was established in December 2010. The committee's mission is to synthesize and summarize the science and information pertaining to current and future impacts of climate change upon the United States; and to provide advice and recommendations toward the development of an ongoing, sustainable national Assessment of global change impacts and adaptation and mitigation strategies for the Nation. Within the scope of its mission, the committee's specific objective is to produce a National Climate Assessment.

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION CONTACT: Dr. Cynthia Decker, Designated Federal Official, National Climate Assessment and Development Advisory Committee, NOAA, Rm. 11230, 1315 East-West Highway, Silver Spring, Maryland 20910, (Phone: 301-734-1156, Fax: 301-713-1459, Email: Cynthia.Decker@noaa.gov.)